

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PROJECT MANAGEMENT SOFTWARE UTILIZATION PERFORMANCE VOCABULARY COMPOSITION

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Abstract

The paper deals with the IT/IS impact on the performance of engineering projects. The objective of the study is to investigate the level of a project management software package utilization from real package data. The investigation is considered to be a unique one. The methods used in the study are concerned with lexical, statistical and cognitive analyses. The hypothesis of the paper is regarded with the detailed innovation vocabulary composition study. The perspective of the paper is concerned with the vocabulary studies to be developed and expanded.

Keywords: project management, real project data, software package, coordination analyses, information systems, technologies, composition etc.

The experimental part

The analyses done are based on a running standard the length of which comes to 14740 lexical units. The impact of information technologies (IT) and information systems (IS) on organizations are numerous; they involve new organizational structure, and result in the increase of the productivity of the individuals to facilitate the increase of the organizational productivity. These systems allow to reduce the size of organizations to facilitate the coordination inside. Better coordination allows to release more complex projects to bring together many factors. The IT and IS help organizations to improve their detection capability, and capacity to response.

The innovative vocabulary fully corresponds its advanced engineering, and scientific sphere; the objective of the paper is concerned with the vocabulary description in full.

The composition of the innovative vocabulary is rather complicated because the scientific and engineering sphere dictates to develop a highly organized systematic vocabulary. The vocabulary systematizes groups of lexemes to be regarded like pure scientific and engineering the same time. These systematic groups are the main characteristics of the analyzed vocabulary. It is not advisable to divide such groups organizations into small fragments but recommended to analyze them upon the whole. The highly specialized groups are represented by the following groups combinations. They are: the impacts of IT/IS on the performance of engineering projects; IT/IS engineering projects are really based on real data projects; the objective is to investigate the level of utilization from real project data; results stemming from non-parametric tests, and correlation analyses show etc. The fact is that the above examples suggest such specialized groups to represent in reality the sentences but these models can be considered like innovative separate and well developed groups. Such interpreting is dictated by the engineering science sphere the vocabulary develops. The above examples are existing models the science chooses. Such a division of the analyzed vocabulary helps understand

the present science and technology sphere. The presented fragments create a vivid picture of the demonstrated process at once. It gives the immediate picture the engineering science displays. Such groups formations are suggested to be called accomplished developed specialized groups which can interpret the specialized incoming professional information. The information is likely to be a very actual one as specialized groups occupy the central position of the vocabulary studied. These professional groups submit the exact & detailed information to concern the problem. Inside the groups there are subjects and predicates like in traditional sentences but the innovative science and engineering professional information in systematically organized and completed specialized groups occupy their special place in the highly professional vocabulary. Besides there are also infinitive specialized groups to concretize the information submitted: to produce the size of organizations to facilitate the coordination within the organizations; to investigate the level of utilization of the project management software package; to make better decisions; to maintain a competitive advantage to implement an effective project management; to investigate the level of a project management software; to examine the relationship between system utilization and project performance; to achieve economy of scale; to reduce general and administrative costs; to ensure a better inventory turnover. The above infinitives groups help fix the details of some very important science and engineering events; sometimes the infinitives of further action are widely used in the observed vocabulary; to connect IT/IS to the characteristics of the project to improve the project performance; to simultaneously manage more projects to reduce the duration of projects etc. The first infinitive fulfils the function of the right attribute, and the second one realizes the function of the further action. Participle 2 constructions are observed in the specialized vocabulary: the information required for good operations of the organization; the subsystems usually found in a project management software packages; a project management software developed by an

engineering construction; the variables studied; an engineering construction firm recognized internationally; the variables considered in this study; the measures used in the existing literature; a subsystem divided by the projection duration etc. The above Participle2 constructions represent the function of the right attribute. These constructions give the possibility to verify some engineering process or an event to the corresponding form of which the Participle 2 construction refers to. Many components special words combinations are not rare phenomena in the studied vocabulary. These professional words combinations submit the verifying information to describe the obtained information. Let's address the illustrative material: perfect management software utilization, project management software package, the data collection process, project manager software' collective organizational management, project planning management system, enterprise software technologies, real project data, an engineering construction firm, social care information systems the engineering process management subsystem. Very valuable information comes from the tables to refer to project management subsystems. The tables represent all the information divided into two columns. The first one represents subsystems, and the second one describes functions. The subsystems analyzed are expressed by two- and many components words combinations to disclose all the information they involve. The examples of such words combinations: project definition, active planning, environmental management, health and safety management; estimating process management, working hours management, document control, document management, engineering process management procurement management, cost management, construction activity management. The above many components words combinations add a new innovation bloc to disclose the software subsystems vocabulary. The subsystems functions are represented by the following many components words combinations like project parameters, project characteristics. The above functions correspond to the following words combinations: highly specialized employees, classification codes, persons in charge, dates, contract type etc. As for the activity planning (to be represented like a system), the corresponding vocabulary specialized words combinations are fixed by schedule project activities and specific professional software. Environment management demands environmental plans management preventions, training and follow-up actions on inspections and accidents lexemes and words combinations. The health and safety management subsystem uses health and safely plans management, preventive measures, education, preventions inspections and follow up actions on accidents and incidents lexemes and words combinations. The estimating process management subsystem displays the specialized words combinations like detailed estimate of project, project work breakdown structure, work passages etc. The working hours management subsystem corresponds to the following specialized words combinations (many component ones): documents and active documents processes. The document control subsystem uses internal and external control documents generated during the execution of the

project specialized word combinations. The document management subsystem includes the following vocabulary units: documents and archive documents processes. The engineering process management subsystem suggests such professional words combinations: equipment and materials resulted from engineering recording, purchase requisitions, engineering tools, interface with engineering tools. The procurement management subsystem deals with procurement processes, project purchasing, training contract administration, logistics, procurement follow-up and inspection, material management on site etc. The cost management subsystem corresponds to the following words combinations: the project budget follow up, invoicing and payments follow up etc. The constructive activities management subsystem refers to the words combinations: construction contracts, construction progress, activities management implementation.

So now we understand that each subsystem becomes the information source for other systems. And then f.ex the document management subsystem receives the information from the procurement management and engineering management subsystems. So a new block of professional engineering many component words combinations join the analyzed vocabulary : project definition, activity planning, environment management, health and safety management estimating process management, construction activity management, project management software package, working hours management, document control, cost management, procurement management, engineering process management, document management etc. So that is an additional bloc of inventory managements words combinations to refer to the Interaction between two subsystems The analysis of this vocabulary showed that the studies on the impacts of IT/IS engineering projects are rarely based on real data of projects. To recognize this limitation the objective of this paper is to investigate the level of use of the project management software vocabulary additions based on primary sources of project data. Specifically the objective of the vocabulary is to derive a software utilization profile for the best performance projects from the firm and to examine the relationship between system utilization and project performance. The specialized vocabulary has got all the inventory to require the project management software utilization problem; the inventory is highly scientific and engineering; the composition of the lexemes belonging to the analyzed vocabulary is of the Latin origin. The old Germanic lexemes are rather rare here but they are to fulfill some service functions. As for old Germanic verbs (irregular ones) they are rather limited in number; the studied scientific problem needs this 100% pure scientific style. The studied vocabulary uses the irregular verbs and common lexemes to be referred to the common lexemes register (Germanic verbs) to be used together with the Latin ones. As for the above constructions used they are really unique, and innovative ones; the composition of such a vocabulary is considered to be very complicated. It was noticed that the specific detailed information to concern groups and units to remind the real sentences with subjects and predicates specialized groups manifested like the parts of

Participle and Infinitive constructions are used. As for mono lexemes they are of rare usage and the most of them are represented by many component words combinations. The scheme of the vocabulary used is rather innovative like the science itself to be interpreted by the very vocabulary to concern project management software utilization. The way the information to be submitted is rather revolutionary. The problem is realized by long chains of sentences to have used subordinate clauses, and many details used to be verified. The problem shows the software level to be used, and some of the subsystems appear to be linked to project performance. The choice of scientific and highly specialized lexemes (of the Latin origin) used is rather unique.

The fact is that IT/IS is considered to be innovation tools for organizational management, and besides IT includes communication vehicles and tools to have included Internet, Intranet, e-mail, Videoconference etc to have ensured the linking between IS and individuals within organizations. And besides IS includes software and data bases to have used in the organizational management process, f. ex. ERP system, project planning management system etc. Many studies on the impacts of IT/IS on organizations to concern the determination, analysis and quantizing of the impacts of IT/IS on productivity, improvement of processes and innovation etc. were carried down. The above information says about innovation additional blocs of the vocabulary analyzed. These blocs bring various vocabulary specialized units to correspond the above information. First come vocabulary blocs to refer to the studies on the impacts of IT/IS: determination, analysis, quantizing, impacts, coordination, reactivity, effectiveness, learning capacities, to achieve economies of sale, to reduce general and administrative costs, organizational processes to ensure better inventory turnover, lack of studies, performance of engineering projects, a recommendation channel between the designers, and the use of data bases, common software, to facilitate the coordination, a complex project, increase in the number of multi-divisional projects, companies having implemented an ERP system, higher light importance to connect IT/IS to the characteristics of a project.

The above illustrations are the fragments of new additional blocs of specialized lexemes. These fragments are of different compositions; they differ in length to concern these fragments, and their fillings. Mono specialized lexemes are in wide use; there are examples to regard specialized and developed professional groups and the cases when the specialized lexemes sufficiently use conjunctions and prepositions (and, on, in, between, of, for etc). Infinitives developed groups are widely used here; Participle constructions are being practiced too (Perfect Participles, f.ex.). Two components specialized words combinations are fixed as well as three components and four components ones (project management software packages). Inside many components words combinations there can be the propositions, f.ex., a significant correlation between the efficiency of the project management system etc). Now such components words combinations are much longer But such words combinations are available, they do ex-

ist (f.ex. the quality of the project management information system, and the frequency of the use of PMIS has a positive impact on the performance of the project). Such long specialized many component words combinations which consist of many finished fragments links are joined by the conjunction "and". These fragments of the studied vocabulary help estimate the importance of the vocabulary and understand that most vocabulary units are based on real project data and the level of use of a project management software and its link with the performance of projects.

Conclusions. So the investigation was carried out to be concerned with a specialized professional engineering project management software utilization, and project management (PMSU and PM). Upon the whole the scientific vocabulary includes the lexemes to answer the problem of PMSU PM science sphere. The vocabulary is complete, complex to be able to interpret any science innovating problem to regard PMSU PM. Its composition is varied. It unites mono specialized lexemes, many component words combinations, the length of which can vary sufficiently. Infinitives and Participles construes developed are widely used in different functions. Specialized construes like developed sentences to have possessed subjects and predicates are interpreted upon the whole and which can be considered as completed performance, and systematically organized groups of lexemes. The last vocabulary bloc formation is regarded like a highly innovative one. Thin vocabulary divisions help realizing more complex projects to bring the best results to understand the essence of the analyzed problem. Such vocabulary peculiarities show the level of use of the software and some of its subsystems to be linked to project performance The analyzed vocabulary was thoroughly investigated to use different methods to have enclosed cognitive analyses, statistical, sociolinguistic etc. The studied vocabulary keeps not only the lexical units to depict the problem but also tables, f. ex., to concern project management software subsystems like interactions between subsystems, variables studied or CPI performance levels. The conclusive division of the vocabulary manifests the results to have been divided into the following subdivisions: software usage time and subsystems intensity of use with the table subsystems intensity mean scores table included.

As for the divisions it has got software usage time subdivision; as for results they are presented in detail. All the presented subdivisions of the above vocabulary were thoroughly analyzed. For project management practitioners the studied vocabulary provides rather broad insights for the engineering projects. The above vocabulary showed that project performance is defined in terms of schedule, scope and cost. The results of the vocabulary researches are under the project performance criteria. Another limited project would bring different findings. So the project management system data vocabulary is organized like, f.ex. its standard scheme of a science project criteria show. All the vocabulary data collected during the experiment are presented through the experimental procedure to be reliable and sufficient.

References

1. Lavrova, Alexandra. Genome& Bioinformatics Lexicon Research History/ Alexandra Lavrova // Norwegian journal of the International Sciences.-2020. №39. -V.4, P.33-38. DOI
2. Lavrova, Alexandra. Interactive Robots Electrons Skin manufacturing Vocabulary Investigation/Alexandra Lavrova // Global Science Potential SPB: the fund of science and culture development. № 7 (124), 2021. P.195-200. VAK
3. Lavrova, Alexandra. Laptop Developing History Vocabulary// Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift: Satteldorf, Artmedia.-2021.№24. -P.56-59. DOI
4. The Oxford Universal Dictionary Illustrated on Historical Principles.- Oxford Univ. Press, 1974.